

The Dark Theory

A New Perspective on Electromagnetic Medium and Space

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Abstract

This paper introduces **The Dark Theory**, a proposed conceptual framework based on the existence of a new particle and its medium for electromagnetic waves. The theory suggests that electromagnetic waves do not travel through an empty vacuum but rather through a subtle medium composed of these newly theorized particles. This challenges the classical notion of "empty space" and opens new possibilities for understanding wave propagation, energy transfer, and the fundamental nature of space.

Keywords

The Dark Theory, Electromagnetic Medium, New Particle, Space Properties, Wave Propagation, Particle Properties and Anti-Particles or Anti-Medium

1. Introduction

The nature of electromagnetic wave propagation has long been described by Maxwell's equations and the theory of relativity, which claim that EM waves can travel through the vacuum of space without requiring a medium. However, historical concepts such as the "aether" once proposed the idea of a medium, though it was later discarded due to lack of evidence.

This paper reintroduces a modernized version of that idea **The Dark Theory** which proposes the existence of a new, particle and a medium that fills space and enables the propagation of EM waves. There are two types of particles which make medium and space. First one is the **In-active particle** and second one is **active particle**.

2. Background

Classical physics has explained electromagnetic waves as self-propagating electric and magnetic fields. Quantum physics added photons into the equation, yet the question remains: *what is the actual “space” these photons move through?*

And what is the Darkness?

This is the biggest question many scientist says that darkness is nothing ‘cause it’s created by our brain but it is not really true. I know that the darkness is nothing but it is something which we ignore. The darkness is the key of my theory.

In **The Dark Theory**, we explore the possibility that this “**space**” is not truly empty, but filled with an ultra-fine medium composed of unknown particles that do not interact, and we will explore about the **Darkness** and its strange type of **particles** with its properties and working

3. Core Concepts of The Dark Theory

3.1 The New Particle

In-Active Particle (Aseton)

The first particle, tentatively named the **Aseton**, which has the following properties:

- It is active particle and mass less
- Interact with everything
- It is so small, we can’t find that how much small is this, mean it’s smallest universally
- Present in everywhere, around us and in entire universe
- Don’t destroy information and make the medium

Active Particle (Axiton)

The second particle, tentatively named the **Axiton**, this is anti-particle of Aseton. properties:

- It is In-active particle and mass less
- Don’t interact with anything, and we can make Axiton though technology (maybe)
- It is so small, we can’t find that how much small is this, mean it’s smallest universally
- Not present in everywhere, present just in specific places
- State of information destroyer and it don’t let thing to go.
- The speed of Axiton is > speed of light (maybe). And they are connected (entangled)

3.2 The Medium

When we close our eyes, what we found, the darkness? Yes the darkness, according to scientist it happen due to absence of light and our brain make that black image in our brain 'cause in no light condition our brain confuse.

According to research we see darkness because of our brain misinformation and due to this statement of scientist we all ignore the darkness, the darkness is everything, the particles about which we talk that was the particle of darkness. The Aseton and Axiton make the darkness and the The Dark Theory Medium is also a Darkness.

The Darkness is the space in which we live and it is state of everything mean it provide medium not just for EM waves it provide medium of everything that's is why it is state of everything.

When it's in-active and don't interact with anything then how we see the darkness?

Because no matter the light is not interacting but we can see the medium (darkness), because the color of darkness is Black due to this we see black, let take an example when something don't reflect backlight 100% mean object absorb 100% light so what we see, the object in black color. So this proof that we can see the Quanhighther. It's not important to see everything in the presence of light, we can see the object when no light is reach form any object to our eyes.

So here the light is travelling through that medium and don't interact, if it does not interact meant it will not reflect any light this makes the no light condition in the presence of light and hence we see the medium (darkness).

Quanhighther

Quanhighther is tentatively name of the medium.

The **Aseton** collectively form a dynamic medium **Quanhighther** which fills space and allows EM waves to pass through it.

The Quanhighther provide a medium for Electromagnetic waves like Light. The medium is In-Active because the particles are In-active.

The EM waves like light (Photon) pass through Aseton without any Energy loss and Speed.

The Quanhighther Particles are so small so they pass from anything like human, planets and atoms (electrons) etc.

It is possible to make these particles active, if we do! Then that could be dangerous because it can emit radiation and a lot of heat in a second.

The color of Quanhighther is Darkness/Blackness

Working

Quanleather/Anti-Medium

Quanleather is tentatively name of the anti-medium

This is the opposite of Quanhighther which is present in **active form**.

We know that every action has an equal but opposite reaction here opposite medium is present but the **reaction is not equal**.

It similar in color of **Quanhighther** but its working method is completely different from Quanhighther the working is opposite and not equal.

It accepts the given **information** but after acceptance of information they destroy the information and radiate large amount of **energy**. Its active particle is called **Axiton**

The photon can't pass through Axiton or Anti-particle because the Anti-particles Axiton have much power than photon/xyz. The emitted energy so high in power.

May be the anti-medium Is present is Black Holes, but it's not confirmed.

When any person enters in **Quanleather**, it will effect person according to its power, anti-medium power is **variable** it's not constant.

The Particles of this medium are entangled they are useful for communication in the entire universe.

Working

3.3 Relation with Space

According to theory the New Particles are part of space and they made the space, but this is not confirmed, it is just a hypothesis.

4. Theoretical Implications

Wave Propagation: EM waves travel in the Dark Medium, without disturbing the medium, this is not working as sound wave, sound waves need medium disturbance but here for EM waves they need medium but they propagate without disturbance in medium.

Vacuum Reinterpretation: The vacuum of space is redefined not as empty, but as filled with Quanhighters

Energy Transfer: The Anti-Medium transfer energy as sound wave do but with some special properties,

5. Limitations and Open Questions

- No current experimental proof for Axiton and Aseton
 - What is the origin of this medium?
 - How can we detect or interact with this medium?
 - Does this theory violate or extend known physics laws?
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6. Conclusion

The Dark Theory provides a fresh perspective on the medium of electromagnetic waves and the nature of space itself. While speculative, the theory opens new discussions about the fabric of the universe and the unseen structures that may exist within it. Future experimental and theoretical work may validate, refine, or disprove this model, but the possibilities it introduces are worthy of consideration. And if we are able to emit Axiton then we can communicate everywhere in the entire universe because these particles are entangled with each other automatically.